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Video Presentation as a Report in Elementary Physics Laboratory

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INTRODUCTION

Traditional engineering curriculum includes introductory physics laboratory work. It can be implemented either on its own course or integrated to physics theory courses. Students widely agree that the skills learned in introductory physics laboratory are important but achieving those skills usually need more work compared to theory courses. Skills that are connected to introductory physics laboratory are designing and implementing an experiment, making measurements suitable for the task, processing the data, assessing the uncertainty of the results and reporting the task and the results in technically and scientifically proper way. Since 2010, Tampere University of Applied Sciences physics introductory laboratory course has included a laboratory work that students design, plan and implement by themselves at the end of the course. The concept of the own laboratory work has developed

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during the years. During first years, it was reported as traditional written report to the teacher. The idea that students would learn a lot if they were introduced to other students' work, led to reporting these works as posters in a common poster session within the student group. The poster session also included peer assessment of the other students' work. The latest step of development process is to change the reporting of the own laboratory work as a short video. Video gives more possibilities to reporting and they can be peer assessed asynchronously while poster session demands that all students have to be present at the same time. In video reporting, students also learn modern communication and reporting skills.

1 CHALLENGES IN INTRODUCTORY PHYSICS LABORATORY

Typical preferred learning outcomes of the introductory physics laboratories base on designing and implementing laboratory tasks and reporting them in technically and scientifically proper way. The laboratory work can also be used to support and deepen the understanding gathered in physics theory courses. According to Holmes and Wieman undergraduate laboratories that are designed to support theory courses, do not necessary improve grades. Instead, laboratory courses that focus on improve students' experimental and intellectual abilities, can succeed, and offer great opportunities to learn experimentation, reasoning and critical thinking skills. [1]. An example of laboratories with such design are ISLE laboratories [2]. Such learning outcomes are important engineering skills. There are still a number of challenges in the laboratories that rise not only from students or laboratory practices but outside. Laboratory teaching is more expensive than traditional theoretical teaching mainly because facilities are more expensive and the guidance in laboratory needs more teaching resources per student. This may lead to the process that due to financial reasons, the laboratory type of learning is reduced in engineering curricula.

Students' experiences on elementary laboratory courses vary depending the goals and implementation. Experiences of the laboratory have been reported to be negative or dull mainly because tasks, working and the solution methodology have been pre-stated [3]. On the opposite, a survey from Australia shows that physics laboratory work provides students with many important skills that they think they do need in the future. Students saw laboratory work useful, understandable, interesting and enjoyable [4].

Considering the learning outcomes of an introductory physics laboratory course, typical difficulties lie in the core of understanding measurement and interpreting data gathered. Students' view on a measurement may see the measured values as "point-like" or exact, without any uncertainty [5]. The concepts of error analysis are very difficult for students. Applying statistical methods to a set of data may be difficult for university students even after the laboratory course [6]. It seems natural in the context of average person's view on measuring data. The errors or uncertainties are not often seen in everyday life.

One of the key skills connected to laboratory teaching is reporting. Traditionally students write a complete lab report on every measurement task they complete. According to student feedback, the reporting is typically seen as the hardest part of laboratory course. This is obvious, because the most difficult parts like data processing, error estimations and interpreting the results in professional way, need a lot of time and effort. Some practices have been introduced to reduce the students' workload in reporting. In "sElf approach", students focus on different parts of report on different laboratory tasks. Finally, at the end of the

laboratory course a “mother of all reports” is finished on the last laboratory measurement task [7].

2 IMPLEMENTATION OF PHYSICS LABORATORIES AT TAMPERE UAS

2.1 Overall picture on physics laboratory courses

In Tampere UAS, engineering curriculum contains two courses that include physics laboratory practices. The First course “Basics of measuring and reporting” 3 cr, introduces students all basic skills they need to succeed in elementary laboratory. The skills include making good measurements and completing the measurement logbook, the necessary mathematics to complete data analysis and error estimations and the necessary reporting skills to complete a proper report. The course is taught together with physics, mathematics and communications teacher. The design and implementation of the course are described in [8]. In the course students work on pairs and complete three different measurement and reporting tasks which focus on different type of measurement tasks, necessary mathematics and fluency and formalities of traditional written reporting.

After completing the first course, students can enter to the second course “Laboratory works of physics” , 3 cr, which contains four pre-stated laboratory tasks and the last task in which students design, implement and report the laboratory work themselves. In pre-stated tasks, students make measurements in pairs but the reporting is individual, two reports per student. The self-designed laboratory work is planned, implemented and reported in pairs. In the course, students are expected to be familiar with basics of measuring, data-analysis and reporting.

2.2 Self-designed laboratory work, idea and reporting

Since 2010, the physics laboratories have included a final laboratory work that students design, implement and report in pairs. The main goal in of this change was to give students a real opportunity to design laboratory activity in the beginning of their studios, not only just follow laboratory work instructions that someone else has designed. Teachers have only a guiding and consulting role. The students themselves do all major decisions like choosing the subject, planning the measurements, designing the equipment, and reporting. During first years, reporting was made in traditional way. Students wrote a formal written report to teacher.

The idea of different form of reporting rose from the need that the designed laboratory works were so rich with ideas and perspectives, that students could learn a lot from others if they were aware from other students’ work. Therefore, since 2013 the reporting was implemented with posters. The course has ended to the poster session in which students present their work to the others. The poster session format solved the problem with sharing the ideas and learning from others but brought some other negative aspects. The quality of data-analysis dropped, even though students were reminded that all the calculations and other formalities must be made although they are not explicitly written out. The quality of posters and presentations varied also a lot. The poster was not concerned as serious form of reporting as normal formal written report. The poster sessions took also a lot of time in which all students and teacher had to be present. The sessions were also very tight in schedule and did not leave enough time to needed discussions.

To tackle the challenge of quality and hurry in presenting and reporting, a new method was piloted in spring semester 2018. The idea was to report self-designed laboratory work as video presentation. Videos can be watched asynchronously so students can watch and comment others work online beforehand. Teacher can also watch the videos beforehand and the session time can be used effectively just peer- and teacher feedback and assessment. The pros and cons on different reporting methods are presented in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Pros and cons of different reporting methods

Method	Traditional written report	Poster	Video
Pros	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal • Respected • Familiar 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presented to peers • Peer assessed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to share • Asynchronous presentation • Modern way of communication
Cons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No peer assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult to design • Synchronous presentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May focus on non-important issues

3 EXPERIENCES AND RESULTS OF PILOTING VIDEO REPORTING

3.1 Background

The student group chosen to pilot the video reporting included 32 second-year bachelor-level students studying ICT engineering. The idea of video reporting was presented to the student group in the beginning of the elementary physics laboratory course. The first four pre-stated laboratory tasks were reported in traditional way and the video reporting was applied only on the last, self-designed laboratory work. Student experience was gathered with survey at the end of the course.

3.2 Implementation

Self-designed laboratory work begun with a planning session in which student pairs were asked to plan their work carefully beforehand. At the end of the session students had a written plan that included following.

- Target of the work
- Time and place of implementation
- List of quantities to be measured and a methods to measure them
- Chart or schema of the measurement
- List of equipment needed
- How the results are presented
- How the error estimations are made?
- Legal statement that reminds that student group must obey national law and is responsible for measurements

After planning there were two laboratory sessions, 3 hours each, to make the necessary measurements. Students can also borrow some measurement equipment outside the laboratory in case of field measurement. The report itself was specified to cover all similar contents that formal written report, but in a form of spoken, presented video. The visual part of video was asked to contain pictures, graphs, charts and other visual elements that support reporting. The video length was asked to be between 5 to 10 minutes.

Students were introduced briefly how to make a video from PowerPoint presentation and using screen capture software. A common YouTube channel was created for video sharing and streaming. The idea of making a video report was positively adopted by the student group. The videos were allowed to be published in any video service and the links to the videos were asked to be sent as discussion openings in course's Moodle discussion forum. Peer assessments were answers to the discussion openings. In this form of returning every video and every peer assessment is public within the student group. Peer assessments were asked to be published within two days after publications of videos. Teacher decided which videos were assessed by each student group and every video got at least two peer assessments. In the final lecture of the course the student group was divided for 2 subgroups and the videos were watched and discussed and teacher's assessments were published.

3.3 Overall results

Overall, students managed well. The laboratory works were designed according the criteria specified in chapter 3.2. Measurements were made autonomously and students finished their video reports. In reporting, technique and the use of necessary software was not a problem for any pair of students. All videos and peer assessments were published on time. The method itself had no such flaws that would prevent its use in the future.

3.4 Student experience

Student experience was gathered with a survey at the end of the course. 16 of 32 possible students answered to the survey. Results from the survey show that technically producing and publishing a video was not difficult for students. This can be seen from answer distributions presented in fig. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Producing a video

Fig. 2. Publishing the video

Instead, planning and making the contents of the video (core of reporting) was seen a little bit more difficult, but not overwhelming by the students, this can be seen from the answer distribution in fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Making the contents of the video

Students were also asked about their experiences in different phases of making a self-designed laboratory work. Choosing the subject was reported as the most difficult phase, followed by setting up the questions, what to research. Planning and implementing the measurements and processing the data were reported as the easiest parts of the work, but none of these was reported to be very easy. Reporting was experienced to be somewhere between difficult and easy.

Students were also asked if they could recommend (yes or no) this kind of reporting method in a similar situations or so called normal laboratory tasks where tasks are pre-stated. Distributions of student answers are presented in the following figures fig 4 – 5.

Fig. 4. Recommendation, self-designed

Fig. 5. Recommendation, traditional

From figures 4 and 5 it can be stated that overall, students liked the piloted method of reporting especially in the self-designed laboratory work.

Students were also asked what they would do differently now if they were facing the similar task of designing and reporting an experimental task. The most mentioned issues were

- More careful planning of the work
- Thinking carefully the subject of lab work
- Planning of the measurements

3.5 Teacher experiences

Teacher experience was monitored by discussions with the teacher of the course before, during and after the course. Teacher experience can be summarized as follows.

- In the beginning, insecure feeling about technical readiness of the student group.
- After the instruction session for technical aspects, feeling disappeared.
- The proper content must be highlighted *over the technical aspects*
 - The substance quality of reporting was still not good enough
 - Error estimations missed on many reports
- Technical quality was good
- This method will be used in the future, but special care and effort will be put in contents of reporting

4 CONCLUSIONS

Overall, the piloting of the video-reporting in self-designed laboratory work can be called as a minor success. All students managed to finish their reports on time and system of peer assessment and sharing report videos among student group worked. In attitude level students liked the method of video reporting and recommended it strongly in a similar situations but not as strongly in tasks which are pre-stated.

New different method of reporting somehow took attention away from the core of reporting. There were still some lack of quality in contents of reports, even though report videos were asked to follow the formalities of a written report.

Considering students' answers of what they would do differently now clearly show that even the lack of straight success in the measurements and results lead to the professional growth concerning the whole laboratory work. Students were able to point the phase in which they need to do better in the future. In the case of the lack of success, the reason was found "in the mirror" on the most cases.

Overall, the combination of self-designed laboratory work and video reporting worked quite well on tackling the challenges in laboratory teaching. Task, methodology and reporting was open enough as laboratory work so overall students felt working interesting and enjoyable. The challenge in formalities, seeing the own laboratory work as real measurement task with error estimations and error calculations, still keeps untackled. It seems that it is very difficult for students to perform these measurement formalities unless they are asked to do so.

It is seen that the self-designed laboratory work supports the skills that are needed in engineering profession. Students also appreciate the trust that they are able to design at the early phase of their studies.

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